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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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JURISDICTIONAL ISSUES AND CHOICE OF LAW IN E-COMMERCE IN NIGERIA

By

Amaayeneabasi Ini Enang*

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ABSTRACT

Choice of forum and law are prevalent issues in cross border commercial transactions including cross-border electronic commerce (e-commerce) transactions. This paper identifies this as a problem in Nigeria due to the fact that there is no legislation addressing this issue. Decided cases are all that we refer to in this regard. The objective of this study is to understand the position of the law on choice of law and forum in Nigeria in respect of electronic commerce, and make a comparative analysis on the position in other jurisdictions, to see if there are codified laws. This work adopts an analytical approach to legal research. Using both primary and secondary sources of legal research materials. This work finds that there is no codified law on choice of forum and choice of law to address the complexities of cross border e-commerce transactions in Nigeria. This work recommends that for the purpose of cross border electronic commerce transactions, there should be a codified law, and provisions from the 2008 Rome Convention and Brussels Recast, for example, can be adopted and tailored to fit our legal system, specifically including e-commerce scenarios in the legislation.

Keywords: Choice of Law, Choice of forum, Electronic Commerce, Cross-border transactions

1.0 INTRODUCTION

One of the major issues in e-commerce is the issue of jurisdiction. Especially in deciding which law should govern a particular transaction or place of settlement of disputes across borders. While in traditional commerce, this may not be a cause for concern because parties are identified and known, mostly through personal conversations, mails, and other known means, in e-commerce the sellers are sometimes unknown and contact is less, especially when using social media platforms by contracting parties in different jurisdictions.

Because the internet transcends national boundaries, the phenomenal worldwide growth in internet usage in the past decade or so has been accompanied by a dramatic expansion in B2C contracts across borders. Hornle observed that the Internet is, in its essence, a global network of connections which has led to a massive increase in international contacts and contracts, for consumers and businesses alike and hence multiplied the opportunities for cross-border disputes and conflicts. Once, cross-border litigation was only of relevance to multi-national businesses; now ordinary consumers routinely find themselves embroiled every day in transnational online disputes. For instance, when an eBay sale by a Welsh housewife to a purchaser in the US goes wrong, or a purchase from Amazon by an English consumer fails to arrive or a Scottish laptop is infected with viruses after the download of a free game offered by a Finnish promoter.¹

The increasing prevalence of such cross-border internet transactions underscores the complexity of jurisdictional and choice of law issues, potentially impacting the rights and obligations of parties involved. In other words, the issues under this heading are:

- i. Which court should serve as the forum for hearing the disputes (Jurisdictional issues)
- ii. Which particular system of law should be utilised in determining the dispute (Choice of law issues).

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¹ J Hornle, 'The Jurisdictional Challenge of the Internet' in L Edwards, *Law and The Internet* (Chapter 3, Hart Publishing 2000) 121.

A classic example is as follows: John, who lives in Nigeria ordered and paid for a pair of expensive hand-made shoes from a website operated by a Chinese company. The company's website is hosted by a server located in the United States. Upon receiving John's order, the Chinese company forwarded it to its Vietnamese factory where all its shoes are made. Two weeks later, Ben received a package posted from Vietnam but when he opened it, he discovered that it contains two left shoes. Since then, he has sent numerous emails to the Chinese company asking for his money back but these have all been ignored.

Assuming John decides to go to court, will jurisdiction rest with the Nigerian courts, or will he have to travel to China, where the company is based, to United States where the website was hosted, or perhaps Vietnam, from where the shoes were dispatched? Having decided which court is to adjudicate on the dispute, that court would then have to apply relevant choice-of-law rules in order to determine which country's system of law will govern the dispute at hand.

It is very common for parties who enter into such transnational contracts to deal expressly with these issues through the insertion of forum selection and choice of law clauses. For example, the online contract entered into between Facebook and its users contains a clause that, 'You will resolve any claim you have with us arising out of or relating to the Statement of Facebook in a state or federal court located in Santa Clara County (*Choice of forum*). The laws of the State of California will govern this Statement, as well as any claim that might arise between you and us (*Choice of law*)'.²

Clauses of this nature are usually included in online business-to-consumer (B2C) contracts at the behest of the business rather than the consumer. Rowland, Kohl and Charlesworth (RKC) remark that it is understandable why businesses engaged in online trade especially those with a clientele scattered all over the world would wish to insert clauses like these into their agreements since from their point of view, "such clauses provide significant protection and certainty, and not enforcing them discourages such trade". As they go on to point out, however, this must be set against the fact that "for consumers, they are troublesome, because they often deprive them of a realistic chance of a remedy; thus, enforcing them is likely to

² Facebook, 'Terms of Service' <<https://m.facebook.com/legal/terms>> accessed on 1 February 2024.

undermine consumer confidence in transnational online trade.”³ This paper will analyse the position of the law in Nigeria and other jurisdictions with regards to choice of law and forum in cross border e-commerce transactions.

The research methodology employed in this study is doctrinal and analytical. Primary sources of research materials will be used including case laws and statutes from the EU and Nigeria. Secondary sources employed include foreign textbooks from scholarly learned authors, as well as journals from Nigerian learned authors. The jurisdiction which will be analysed in this study is Nigeria, with lessons to learn from the EU.

This paper is structured into 5 sections. The introduction provides an overview of cross border e-commerce and the challenges related to choice of law and forum therein. The second section focuses on determining the applicable court for adjudicating e-commerce disputes in Nigeria and the EU in cases where parties have chosen an applicable court and when they have not. The third section focuses on analysing the applicable law for settlement of cross border disputes in Nigeria and the EU in cases where parties have chosen an applicable court and when they have not. The fourth section makes a comparative analysis between laws on e-commerce in Nigeria and the EU. The paper concludes with recommendations including the enactment of e-commerce laws with internet jurisdiction and choice of law provisions contained therein, as well as parties resorting to online dispute resolution in the absence of inputting choice of law and forum clauses in their contracts. And lastly, parties should ensure at all times to include choice of law and forum clauses in their contracts.

1. DETERMINING THE APPROPRIATE COURT FOR ADJUDICATING THE DISPUTE

The significance of this issue is highlighted by RKC who stated that the choice of court “is often a hotly disputed issue” and that the manner in which this issue is settled “is often a matter of great importance to the parties.”⁴

1.1 Position in Nigeria

i. Where Parties Have Chosen an applicable Law

³ D Rowland, U Kohl and A Charlesworth, ‘Information Technology Law’. 2017 (Routledge) 236. in A Iwobi, *The legal regulation of electronic contracting in Nigeria in the age of Jumia and Konga*. In Modern Essays on Nigerian Law. (Cambridge Scholars Publishing 2019) 256.

⁴ Ibid

In Nigeria, many of the principles used in determining the appropriate court and law are obtained from common law. This is because, unlike the European Union as will be analysed below, which has regulations governing forum and choice of law selection, Nigeria does not have. Thus, in Nigeria, in the event of a dispute arising from the parties' agreement or any part of it and which necessitates a court action, such action should only be brought by the aggrieved party in the particular foreign court named in the clause. Most often than not, this clause also comes embedded with it, the provision that the law of that country shall apply to the transaction. Thus, the current position of the law in Nigeria regarding this clause is the product of the decision of the English courts.

The attitude and position of the Nigerian courts to foreign jurisdiction clauses is that the clauses do not oust the jurisdiction of the courts to entertain suits commenced in breach of the parties' express stipulations to that effect "as the courts have the discretion to assume jurisdiction notwithstanding the presence of the clause; but it is a discretion which in the ordinary way and in the absence of strong reason to the contrary, will be exercised in favour of holding the parties to their bargain."⁵ In other words, Nigerian courts have exercised discretion as to whether to be bound by the Parties' choice or not. In doing so, they follow the test set by Brandon J. in *Owners of Cargo Lately Laden On-Board Ship or Vessel Eleftheria v. Owners of Ship or Vessel Eleftheria* (The Eleftheria).⁶

Thus, in the locus classicus case of *Sonnar (Nig) Ltd v Partenreedri Ms Nordwind*⁷ (the Nordwind case) the issue before the Supreme Court was whether Clause 3 of the parties' Bill of Lading ousted the trial Federal High Court's (Lagos) jurisdiction to entertain the Plaintiffs' action. In this case, the Plaintiffs who were Nigerian companies had entered into a contract with the Defendants for the delivery of rice from Bangkok to Lagos on board the vessel, M.V Nordwind owned by the first Defendant (the carrier) who carries on business in Germany. Clause 3 of the parties' Bill of Lading had provided that-

⁵ *Nika Fishing Co. Limited v Lavina Corporation* [2008]16NWLR(Pt. 1114) 509.

⁶ (1969)1 Lloyd's L. R 237 at P.242 – This decision currently represents the position of the law in England and same has been followed by the courts in subsequent cases. See *The El Amiya* (1981)2 L.R. 119 and *Trendtex Trading Corporation J. Credit Suisse* (1982) A.C 679.

⁷ *Owners of Cargo Lately Laden On-Board Ship or Vessel Eleftheria v. Owners of Ship or Vessel Eleftheria* [1987] 4 NWLR(Pt. 66) 520.

Any dispute arising under the Bill of Lading shall be decided in the country where the carrier has his principal place of business and the law of such country shall apply except as provided elsewhere herein.

Upon an action at the instance of the Plaintiffs before the Federal High Court, in Lagos the Defendants entered appearance and applied for a stay of proceedings on the ground that the parties' contract vested exclusive jurisdiction in the German courts. The trial court agreed with the Defendants and upheld clause 3 of the Bill of Lading. Dissatisfied with the decision of the court, the Plaintiffs appealed to the Court of Appeal which dismissed the Appeal. A further appeal was made to the Supreme Court and the court in reaching its decision reviewed and adopted the test (the Brandon test) laid down by the English court in *The Eleftheria*.⁸ Per Brandon J., in *The Eleftheria* laid down the rule that-

1. Where Plaintiffs sue in England in breach of an agreement to refer disputes to a foreign court, and the Defendants apply for a stay, the English court, assuming the claim to be otherwise within its jurisdiction is not bound to grant a stay, but has discretion whether to do so or not.
2. The discretion should be exercised by granting a stay, unless strong cause for not doing so is shown.
3. The burden of proving such strong cause is on the Plaintiffs.
4. In exercising its discretion, the court should take into account all the circumstances of the particular case.
5. In particular, but without prejudice to (4), the following matters, where they arise, may properly be regarded:
 - a. In what country the evidence on issues of fact is situated or more readily available and the effect of that on the relative convenience and expense of trial as between England and foreign courts.
 - b. Whether the law of the foreign court applies and, if so, whether it differs from English law in any material respects.

⁸ Ibid

- c. With what country either party is connected, and how closely.
- d. Whether the Defendants genuinely desire trial in a foreign country or are only seeking procedural advantages.
- e. Whether the Plaintiffs would be prejudiced because they would-
 - i) Be deprived of security for their claim
 - ii) Be unable to enforce any judgment obtained
 - iii) Be faced with a time bar not applicable in England: or
 - iv) For political, racial, religious or other reasons be unlikely to get a fair trial.

The Supreme Court after evaluating the foregoing factors in *The Eleftheria* added a fifth factor to paragraph 5(e) above, to wit-

v) Where the granting of a stay would spell injustice to the plaintiff as –where the action is already time barred in the foreign court and the grant of stay would amount to permanently denying the Plaintiffs any redress.

The Supreme Court after reviewing the Brandon test applied same to the case and refused staying the proceedings as the circumstances of the case shows that the Plaintiff/Appellant’s case called for the court to assume jurisdiction. The Court arrived at its decision upon evidence indicating that-

1. The Plaintiffs were just three days away from being caught by limitation rules under The Hague Rules applicable to their contract;
2. Under German law, MV Nordwind would not qualify as a carrier; and
3. Staying proceedings would permanently deprive the plaintiff of the right to sue in Germany as the suit would have become statute-barred by then.

The Supreme Court in finding for the Plaintiffs and upholding the jurisdiction of the Nigerian courts to entertain the suit held as follows-

“Nigerian Courts would hold parties to their bargain and give effect to their choice of foreign jurisdiction. However, the parties’ choice of jurisdiction is not

absolute, as the Courts have the discretion to decline to give effect to a stipulation made by the parties' contract conferring jurisdiction on a foreign Court.”

This decision of the Supreme Court has been followed in subsequent cases and same represents the current position of the law and attitude of the Nigerian courts to foreign jurisdiction clauses.

In interpreting foreign jurisdiction clauses, the courts are urged to always interpret it liberally with a view at retaining their jurisdictions⁹ and upon strong reasons not to stay proceedings would always disregard such clauses. However, the burden of proving a strong cause why the court should exercise its discretion not to stay proceeding rests on the Plaintiff. Thus, in *Nika Fishing Co. Limited v. Lavina Corporation*,¹⁰ the Supreme Court while restating its decision in the Nordwind Case held that the court has discretion, but it is a discretion which in the ordinary way and in the absence of strong reasons to the contrary, will be exercised in favour of holding the parties to their bargain.

Therefore, except the Plaintiff establishes to the Court good reasons why the court should assume jurisdiction, the Court would not but rather hold parties to their bargain. However, it should be stated that the discretion given to the courts to stay proceedings in the face of foreign jurisdiction clauses does not extend to admiralty matters.¹¹

On the whole, a choice of forum clause in a contract does not oust the jurisdiction of the Nigerian courts. The courts are at best urged to stay proceedings upon good and proper application. While nothing is mentioned with regards to e-commerce because of the period when this judgment was given, this judgment may be applied as will be seen below.

ii. Where Parties Have Not Chosen an Applicable Law

Flowing from the above, Brandon J's test may be adopted to decide which court will assume jurisdiction. Thus, where there is no forum chosen by parties in a cross-border contract and the matter is before the Nigerian courts, where one party has applied for

⁹ *Emuze v. University of Benin* [2003] 10 FWLR (PT. 170) 1411 and *Peenok Investment Ltd v. Hotel Presidential* [1983] 4 NCLR 122

¹⁰ *Nika Fishing Co. Limited v. Lavina Corporation* [2013] LPELR-22370(CA).

¹¹ Admiralty Jurisdiction Act Cap A5, LFN 2004, s.20

stay of proceedings to enable the matter to be tried in a foreign court, the court has the discretion not to grant same, instead, assume jurisdiction in the matter. Also, the court has the discretion to entertain the matter before it or not because as seen earlier, if the courts have the discretion to be bound or not to be bound by parties' choice of forum in a contract, then in the absence of a forum selection clause, the court has the discretion to rule either way. Lastly, the courts may also take into consideration the tests as set out in the *Sonnar* case.

With respect to e-commerce cross border contracts, Test (5)(a) of the Brandon test, provides that, 'In what country the evidence on issues of fact is situated or more readily available and the effect of that on the relative convenience and expense of trial as between England and foreign courts' will be regarded by the court in exercising its discretion on whether or not to assume jurisdiction. This implies, for example that, if a buyer/user/consumer downloads a software application which never worked after making purchase or subscribing. The phone in question contains the evidence on issue of fact (which is the faulty software application) hence, the Nigerian court may assume jurisdiction in the matter, while taking the other tests into consideration.

1.2 Position in the European Union

In the European Union (EU), Regulation (EU) No. 1215/2012 on Jurisdiction and the Recognition and Enforcement of Judgments in Civil and Commercial Matters (Recast) was enacted to replace the Brussels I Regulation of 2000 (Regulation (EC) No. 44/2001). This was done to provide a more updated framework for determining the appropriate forum for adjudicating disputes arising from contractual or other commercial relationships. Under this regulation, courts in the U.K. and other EU member states used it as the primary legal framework for deciding jurisdictional matters.

i. Position Where Contractual Choice Has Been Exercised

Parties to a contract may agree on the jurisdiction that will handle any dispute, and such an agreement is generally enforceable. Agreements of this type are generally

embodied in forum selection clauses and the basis for their enforcement is that they represent a legitimate exercise of contractual autonomy by the contracting parties.¹²

Article 25 (1) (Recast) contains a new prorogation clause, intended to supersede the former Art.23(1). It provides that:

If the parties, regardless of their domicile, have agreed that a court or the courts of a Member State are to have jurisdiction to settle any disputes which have arisen or which may arise in connection with a particular legal relationship, that court or those courts shall have jurisdiction.

It therefore means that Article 25 will apply even when the parties are both from outside the European Union. At the same time, however, the recognition accorded by Article 25 to contractual autonomy in relation to forum selection clauses is not absolute since it may, in certain circumstances, be circumscribed by the consumer protection measures provided for in Articles 15-16 of the same Act.

ii. Position where Contractual Choice has not Been Expressed

Where there is no agreement on jurisdiction, the basic rule is that defendants are amenable to the jurisdiction in which they are domiciled – in other words, claimants must follow defendants.¹³ In accordance with this basic rule, Art. 4 (Recast) provides that in the absence of a valid forum selection clause, “persons domiciled in a Member State shall... be sued in the courts of that Member State.” The reasoning behind this rule, according to RKC¹⁴ is that “it is fair, all things being equal that the plaintiff has to bring the complaint against the so-far ‘innocent’ defendant, and it is practical because if the defendant is found liable, the judgment is more easily enforceable against him in his or her home jurisdiction.”

This provision may however be displaced by the special jurisdiction conferred by Art. 7(1)(b) which stipulates that in matters relating to a contract, a person domiciled in one Member State may be sued in the courts of another Member State, if the place of

¹² R A Brand, 'The Evolving Private International Law/Substantive Law Overlap in the European Union' in P Mankowski & W Wurmnest (eds), *Festschrift Fur Ulrich Magnus* (Otto Schmidt 2004) 375.

¹³ Ibid

¹⁴ RKC (n 3) 257.

performance of the obligation in question is in that other Member State. Unless otherwise agreed by the parties the place of performance of the obligation shall be-

- i. in the case of the sale of goods, the place where under the contract, the goods *were delivered* or should have been delivered;
- ii. in the case of the provision of services, the place where under the contract, the services *were provided* or should have been provided.

In *Car Trim GmbH v Keysafety Systems Srl*,¹⁵ the European Court of Justice (ECJ) pointed out that Brussels I of 2000 “is silent as to the definition of the concepts of 'delivery' and 'place of delivery' for the purpose of Art. 5(1)(b).” In the absence of clear guidance from the Regulation itself, it fell to the ECJ in this case to seek to pronounce on what constituted the place of delivery in the context of traditional offline contracts. This was a dispute between an Italian manufacturer of airbag systems and German company which sold its components for use in the manufacturing process. The German seller sued for breach of contract in a German court which then asked the ECJ to determine what constituted the place where under the contract, the goods that had been sold were delivered for purposes of Art.5(1)(b). The ECJ held that the place of delivery as conceived by this provision,

Must be determined on the basis of the provisions of the contract. Where it is impossible to determine place of delivery on that basis... that place is the place where physical transfer of the goods took place as a result of which the purchaser obtained or should have obtained actual power of disposal over the goods at the final destination of the sales transaction.

It is observed that Article 7 of the new Brussels Recast of 2012 also is silent as to the definition of the concepts of delivery and place of delivery. Consequently, the ECJ decision in the *Car Trim GmbH* case still applies in the EU.

Hornle has remarked that jurisdictional rules which are based on such territorial connecting factors as the place of the performance of a contract are “highly ambiguous in Internet-related cases” and that this renders the application of conventional jurisdictional rules to Internet disputes “enormously complex, unpredictable and

¹⁵ *Car Trim GmbH v Keysafety Systems Srl* [2010] E.C.R. I-0125.

uncertain”.¹⁶ This point has been re-iterated by RKC who observed that the nature of digital products is such, that quite apart from the contentious issue as to whether they constitute goods or services, there might also be scope for some ambiguity concerning the “place” where they were delivered or provided.¹⁷ To take a simple example, assuming a traveller purchases an iTunes card at Heathrow Airport which he uses to order some music tracks, begins downloading just before boarding his plane to Amsterdam but the downloading is completed upon his arrival in Amsterdam, there is some scope for argument as to the place where the delivery /provision be deemed to have taken place?

Elaborating on this, Hornle asserts that it is often difficult to determine the exact place of performance for the obligation under an e-commerce contract.¹⁸ As an illustration, imagine a contract where a company buys software by way of download. Assume that the provider of the software is a company incorporated and domiciled in France, the buyer/recipient domiciled in Luxembourg uses an Internet service provider (ISP) domiciled in Belgium. The server hosting the software for downloading is located in Ireland. There are (at least) four arguable possibilities for the place of performance of the contract.

- i. The location of the server which hosts the material being downloaded (Ireland): it could be argued that since the contractual obligation is to make available the software, this has been performed in Ireland. However, this could be completely arbitrary and with no obvious connection to either party, and might be moved from time to time. It is thus not an ideal connecting factor.
- ii. The provider’s domicile (France): Since it is from this location that the provider creates and uploads the software onto the server to make it accessible, arguably, this may be regarded as the place of performance of the contract.
- iii. The location of the recipient’s ISP (Belgium): Since the recipient’s browser sends the request for the software and the software is initially received on a server of the recipient’s ISP, it could be argued that this is the place of performance.

¹⁶ Hornle (n 1) 122.

¹⁷ RKC (n 3) 257.

¹⁸ Hornle (n 1) 126.

- iv. The location of the recipient's computer (Luxembourg): Since this is the location to which he actually downloads the software.

While acknowledging such difficulties, RCK opined that “in most cases, the place of business or domicile of the buyer is the place of performance.”¹⁹ If this approach is sustained, it would follow that in the sphere of electronic contracting, if there is no choice of forum clause in the agreement between the parties, and a buyer wishes to sue his seller/supplier, jurisdiction will vest not in the courts of the Member State where the seller/supplier is based (as per Art 4 (Recast)) but in the courts of the buyer's domicile as the place of performance (as per Art. 7 (Recast)). RKC accordingly observe that, “In view of this, online sellers do well to remember to include a choice-of-court clause in their terms, even if it is struck down in some consumer contracts.

iii. Effect of the Consumer Protection Provisions

Chapter II, Section 4 of Brussels I (Recast) contains certain important provisions relating to jurisdiction specifically designed to protect parties who enter into contracts as consumers. The main benefit enjoyed by consumers in this connection is that they are able to litigate in their home jurisdiction, in circumstances where parties to a contract who are not consumers would not ordinarily be entitled to do so.²⁰

Article 17 (Recast) provides that, in any contract concluded by a consumer for purposes outside his trade or profession, jurisdiction is to be determined by the provisions of Section 4 (comprising Articles 17-19) of Brussels I (Recast).

A consumer has been defined in Article 17(1) Brussels I (Recast) as a person who enters into a contract “for a purpose, which can be regarded as being outside his trade or profession”. Where a contract for the sale of goods or the supply of services is a consumer contract and this contract happens to contain a forum selection clause, one effect of the protective provisions in Brussels I (Recast) is that a seller/supplier (that is, the non-consumer) seeking to rely on such a clause to have the case heard in the jurisdiction of his choice, rather than the consumer's domicile, cannot avail himself of Art. 25 Brussels I (Recast) respectively. This is because Art. 19 (Recast) makes it clear

¹⁹ RCK (n 3) 257.

²⁰ H Chen and Y Zhao, 'Choice of Law in Cross-Border E-Commerce Disputes: A Comparative Analysis' (2017) 25 *International Journal of Law and Information Technology* 1, 30.

that the provisions of Section 4 “may only be departed from by an agreement which... is entered into after the dispute has arisen”.²¹

By the same token, in the case of a consumer contract not including a forum selection clause, where the contract falls under the provisions of Chapter II, Section 4, the general rule (Article 4 of Brussels I (Recast)) and special jurisdiction provisions (Article 7 of Brussels I (Recast)) are overridden for determining jurisdictional matters.²²

Art.18(1) (Recast) expressly permits a consumer to bring proceedings against the other party to the contract either-

- (i) In the courts of the Member State where the other party is domiciled or regardless of the domicile of the other party, in the courts where the consumer is domiciled. Or
- (ii) That the non-consumer party though not domiciled is either pursuing or directing his commercial/professional activities within E.U or
- (iii) That the non-consumer party has a branch or agency in the EU;

Whereas, the extension effected by Brussels I (Recast) is that the consumer has the benefit of suing in the Member State of his own domicile not only an EU-domiciled defendant, but also a non -EU domiciled defendant.²³

Thus, while the bulk of the Chapter II jurisdiction rules of the Recast regulation apply only in cases in which the defendant is domiciled in a Member State, the consumer jurisdiction rules are extended to have a global reach.²⁴

1.3 Position in the United States

The principle of contractual autonomy/choice enshrined in old Art.23 of Brussels I is held even more sacrosanct in the U.S than in the U.K/ E.U with the result that forum selection clauses are routinely upheld in U.S courts not only in B2B but also in B2C

²¹ J Yeh, 'Jurisdiction over Cybercrimes: A Framework for Analysis' (2016) 116 *Columbia Law Review* 5, 1162.

²² S Kierkegaard and D W Arner, 'Jurisdiction in Cyberspace: A Theory of International Spaces' (2019) 60 *Harvard International Law Journal* 2, 423.

²³ E B Crawford and J M Carruthers, 'Brussels I bis – the Brussels Regulation recast: closure (for the foreseeable future)' (2013) *Scots Law Times* 89.

²⁴ Brand (n12) 379.

contracts (contrary to the position under Arts 17-19 (Recast)). Thus, if the parties have agreed that a court or the courts of a Member State are to have jurisdiction to settle any disputes which have arisen or which may arise in connection with a particular legal relationship, that court or those courts shall have jurisdiction.

The U.S approach is illustrated by *Carnival Cruise Lines v Shute*,²⁵ where the Supreme Court held that even in a standard form consumer contract, the inclusion of a forum selection clause was not unfair simply because it is onerous to a consumer and such a clause would be upheld where it served a legitimate purpose for example, protecting the business from being exposed to a proliferation of claims by its customers in numerous locations, wishing to bring proceedings in a place where the business has a link, eliminating uncertainty and arguments that might arise regarding the forum and thereby, in the final analysis saving costs which may then be passed on to customers. Commenting on this approach, RCK indicated that, “Apply this to the online world and most choice-of-forum clauses would withstand U.S judicial scrutiny.”²⁶ They however go on to point out that, “Having said that, *Carnival Cruise* concerned an intra-national case (the U.S having multiple State jurisdictions on account of its federal character) and in an international scenario, U.S courts might be more sympathetic to its local customers' plight.

2. DETERMINING THE APPLICABLE LAW FOR COURT APPLICATION

This section will consider Nigeria and the EU's position on choice of law in electronic commerce.

2.1 Choice of Law Position in Nigeria

Similar to the choice of forum position in Nigeria, in the absence of local legislation, Nigerian Courts adopt the traditional common law rules on choice of law in contracts, developed by English Courts. Nigeria's choice of law clauses are commonplace in cross-border contracts. The primary purpose of such clauses is to agree beforehand and avoid uncertainty over the law that would govern any dispute that may arise out of the relationship created by the contract. This is why floating law clauses are

²⁵ *Carnival Cruise Lines v Shute* [1991] U.S. LEXIS 2221; 59.

²⁶ RCK (n 3) 264.

regarded as invalid under common law. Floating law clauses are contractual choice of law clauses that leave the determination of the applicable law open until a later date, or to be determined by one or both of the parties after execution or subject to an event after the date of making the contract.²⁷ In view of this common law prohibition, parties are expected to expressly provide the applicable choice of law that will guide their contract at the time of execution.²⁸

In Nigeria, because of the often cross-border nature of online contracts, it may be the case that a dispute will arise as to the law applicable to the transaction. A choice of law or governing law provision in a contract allows the parties to a contract to agree that a particular country's laws will be used to interpret the contract, even if the contract was executed in a different country.²⁹ This concept is fundamental to questions relating to the formation, validity, interpretation, performance, and enforcement of a contract. It is important to note that forum selection clauses are entirely different from choice of law clauses.³⁰

i. Position where Parties Have Chosen an Applicable Law

Generally, the parties can in their contract determine which law will be applicable in the event of a dispute.³¹ In other words, parties are free to choose the applicable law. The designated law need not have any connection with the location of the contracting parties or the subject matter of the contract. Thus, in *Nika Fishing Co. Ltd v. Lavina Corporation*, the Parties to the bill of lading were a Nigerian importer and an Argentine ship owner/charterer. The bill of lading provided that disputes between the Parties shall be decided "in the country where the carrier has his principal place of business, and the law of such country shall apply...". The Supreme Court of Nigeria ordered a stay of proceedings of the suit pending at the Federal High Court of Nigeria and held that the dispute between the Parties should be decided in Argentina and in accordance with Argentine laws, as agreed in the bill of lading. In his judgment, Niki Tobi JSC,

²⁷ *Trafalgar House Construction (Asia) Ltd & Another v The Owners and/or Demise Charterers of MV* [1999] 2 HKLRD 136, at 142, Mortimer V-P.

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ Tochukwu Martins Itumo, 'Analysing Nigeria's Choice of Law Regime for Cross-Border Contracts' *Mondaq*, (Lagos, 13 March 2023) <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/government-contracts-procurement-ppp/1292344/analysing-nigerias-choice-of-law-regime-for-cross-border-contracts>> accessed on 4 March 2024.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ E Ekanem, 'Online Contracts in Nigeria – An Overview' (2013) 11 *The Nigerian Juridical Review* 80.

held that, “The bill of lading contains the contractual terms between the Parties and therefore binding on the Parties. Parties are bound by the conditions and terms in a contract they freely enter into”. An exception to this rule is the Brandon test in the Eleftheria case³² which has been judicially followed by the Nigerian courts. This position can also be applied in the context of cross border e-commerce transactions.

ii. Judicial Exceptions to the Parties’ Choice of Law

The choice of law clause in a contract is also subject to certain restrictions. These restrictions are regarded as mandatory notwithstanding any contractual arrangement and cannot be avoided by the parties. As such, Nigerian Courts consider its applicability in every case as against the wishes of the parties in the contract. General instances include illegal contracts, contracts rendered void by statute, contracts void on ground of public policy, contracts tainted by fraud and undue influence, or where the choice was not made bona fide and its recognition by the Courts will adversely affect a party’s right in the contract. The Court of Appeal applied public policy considerations in *Hyd Road & Others Tech Ltd v. Abia State Government of Nigeria*, where it held that the Abia State Government cannot seek refuge under the Limitation Law of the State in an international contract which has been performed. The Court reasoned that applying a law that bars the foreign company from seeking redress would “dent Nigeria’s image in the international community and scare away genuine investors”.

iii. Position where Parties have not agreed on a Choice of Law

If the parties have not agreed on a choice of law, it falls on the court to determine the law to apply using the international conflict of law criteria which provides that the law of the jurisdiction that has the most significant relationship to the transaction and the parties with respect to the issue in dispute will control.³³ The jurisdiction of most significant relationship to the parties and the transaction is determined by a variety of factors including:

- a. The place of the contract;

³² Ibid.

³³ Ibid.

- b. The place where the contract was negotiated (*lex loci contractus*);
- c. The place of performance (*lex loci solutionis*);
- d. The law of the Court where the dispute is submitted for trial (*lex fori*),
- e. The location of the subject matter of the contract;
- f. The law governing related transactions; and
- g. The domicile, residence, nationality, place of incorporation, and place of business of the parties.³⁴

In some cases, even though forum selection clauses and choice of law clauses are conceptually different, the courts may conclude that the express choice of forum by the parties without expressly choosing a different law to govern their rights and obligations suffices to establish a strong presumption that the express choice of forum by the parties indicates that the law of the chosen forum should apply.³⁵

In e-commerce, flowing from the above factors, the place where the contract was negotiated may be an issue if it was negotiated over the internet. Thus, pinpointing a particular location may be difficult, except it is agreed that the place of negotiation is where both parties resided at the point of negotiation. Similarly, the place of performance as seen in the EU analogy above will be in the courts of the buyer/consumer/user's domicile.

2.2 Position in the European Union

Whereas there is a dual system in the EU Member States for dealing with the issue of jurisdiction in transnational contractual disputes (that is, Brussels I Recast and the laws of various member states), there is a single regime for determining which particular body of national law is to be applied to disputes of this nature. This regime is embodied in:

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ *Basoroum v Clemessy International* [1999] 12 NWLR 516, 526; *Resolution Trust Corporation v FOB Investment & Property Ltd* [2000] 6 NWLR 246, 260.

1. The original 1980 Rome Convention on the law applicable to contractual obligations (“the Rome Convention”) applies to contracts concluded by 17 December 2009; and
2. EC Regulation No 593/2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I) applies to contracts concluded after 17 December 2009.

i. Position Where Contracting Parties Have Chosen the Applicable Law

The starting point in seeking to determine the law that will govern a particular contract under Rome I is Art. 3(1) which affirms the basic principle of contractual autonomy by providing that, “A contract shall be governed by the law chosen by the parties. The choice shall be made expressly or clearly demonstrated by the terms of the contract or the circumstances of the case.”

Different aspects of a contract may be governed by different laws. Such a situation is contemplated, for instance, by Art 3(1) which goes further to provide: “By their choice the parties can select the law applicable to the whole or to part only of the contract.” Where the parties have specifically selected the law that will apply only to certain aspects of the contract, this opens up the possibility that under the provisions of Rome I, the law applicable to the remaining part of the contract might be the law of some other country.³⁶

Where the contract contains a choice-of-law clause, this will be upheld for most purposes but not necessarily all purposes. For example, if the contract comes within the scope of any public, criminal or other mandatory laws of a state, these cannot be excluded by the applicable law as designated by the choice-of-law clause in effect, these mandatory laws will take priority over relevant aspects of the applicable law.³⁷

ii. The Limits of Contractual Choice in the Context of Rome I

As seen above, online businesses almost invariably incorporate a choice of law clause as a standard term in the contracts they make in an effort to ensure that they are not

³⁶ G Cuniberti, 'Choice of Law and Jurisdiction in Online Contracts: A European Perspective' in *Research Handbook on Electronic Commerce Law* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2019)75.

³⁷ A Green, 'Navigating the Regulatory Landscape of E-Commerce: Choice of Law, Jurisdiction, and Consumer Protection' (2018)41 *Columbia Journal of Law & the Arts* 2, 153.

subjected to the plethora of contractual rules in force in the various countries where they do business.

The danger that arises where the principle of contractual autonomy is allowed to override all other considerations in relation to choice of law is that it can be exploited by the contracting party who is in a stronger bargaining position to prevail on the other contracting party to agree that their respective contractual rights and obligations will be regulated by a legal regime which deprives that other party of certain protections he might otherwise have enjoyed.³⁸ Art.3(3) of Rome I seeks to counter this by providing that,

Where all the other elements relevant to the situation at the time of the choice are located in a country other than the country whose laws have been chosen, the choice (of law) of the parties shall not prejudice the application of provisions of law of that other country which cannot be derogated from by agreement.

This sub-section is designed to prevent a party from resorting to such choice of law clauses in order to evade the regulatory requirements of a state with which a contract is closely connected by choosing the laws of another state, especially in circumstances where these regulatory requirements are there to protect a weaker contractual party such as a consumer.³⁹ As Hornle puts it, where the sub-section applies, a seller or supplier who is usually in a stronger bargaining position cannot contract out of mandatory provisions of consumer protection law which are part of the substantive law of the consumer's residence.⁴⁰ This position is similar to the *Sonnar* case as discussed earlier.

Thus, although choice of law clauses are a valuable tool for online businesses to reduce their exposure to unwanted laws *vis-à-vis* their contracting parties, their effectiveness is circumscribed by the fact that they do not operate to prevent the application of certain non-derogatory or mandatory laws of the state affected. The effectiveness of such choice of law clauses is further limited by the fact that they are only enforceable

³⁸ J Bell, 'Choice of Law and the Internet' (2017) 66 *International and Comparative Law Quarterly* 1, 91.

³⁹ RKC (n 3) 265.

⁴⁰ Hornle (n 1) 127.

against those who consented to them but not strangers to the contract such as third parties who allege violations of intellectual property rights or defamation.⁴¹

iii. Choice of Law in the Absence of Contractual Choice

Art.4(1) of Rome I applies where there is no agreement between the parties concerning the applicable law. It provides that,

- a) A contract for the sale of goods shall be governed by the law of the country where the seller has his habitual residence.⁴²
- b) A contract for the provision of services shall be governed by the law of the country where the service provider has his habitual residence.⁴³
- c) A contract for the sale of goods by auction shall be governed by the law of the country where the auction takes place, if such a place can be determined.⁴⁴
- d) Then go on to provide that if the applicable law still cannot be determined in the light of these rules, then it will be the law of the country that is most closely connected to the contract.⁴⁵

According to Art.19, habitual residence means that

- 1 In the case of a company, its habitual residence is the place of central administration;
- 2 In the case of a natural person acting in the ordinary course of his business activity, his habitual place of residence shall be his principal place of business;
- 3 In cases where a contract is concluded in the course of the operations of a branch, agency or any other establishment, or such a branch/

⁴¹ RKC (n 3) 266.

⁴² EC Regulation No 593/2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations 2009 (Rome I) Art.4(1)(a)

⁴³ Rome I, Art.4(1)(b)

⁴⁴ This is supplemented by Art.4(2) which contemplates that in ambiguous cases (that is, cases governed by more than one or none of these heads) the applicable law will be “the country where the party required to effect the characteristic performance of the contract has his habitual residence.” The phrase “characteristic performance” in this context refers to “non-monetary consideration”, which, in effect, points to the law of the seller/service provider’s habitual residence.

⁴⁵ Rome I, Arts.4(4) and (5).

agency/establishment is responsible for performing the contract, the place where the branch/agency/establishment is located shall be treated as the place of habitual residence.

3. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN NIGERIA AND EUROPEAN LAWS ON ELECTRONIC COMMERCE

In Nigeria, there is no comprehensive law on electronics unlike in the EU, which has the E-Commerce Directive of 2000, specifically providing for e-commerce transactions between member states.

In Nigeria, there are other laws that may apply to e-commerce such as Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, etc.) Act, 2015 which regulates various cybercrimes, such as fraud, identity theft, and data breaches in the online space, directly affecting data subjects; Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) of 2019 and the Data Protection Act 2023 which governs data protection and privacy; the Sale of Goods Act 1893 which governs sale of goods, though some of its provisions are irrelevant to e-commerce transactions. While in the EU, we have E-commerce Directive (2000/31/EC) which provides the foundation for regulating online services, covering aspects such as liability of intermediaries, electronic contracts, and consumer rights in the EU; General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), 2018 which regulates the handling of personal data in the EU, ensuring that companies operating in e-commerce protect consumer privacy and comply with strict data protection rules; Consumer Rights Directive (2011/83/EU) which strengthens consumer protection in online transactions, including clear information requirements, right to withdrawal, and refund policies (in Nigeria, we have the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2018 which aims to protect consumers but does not make provisions for e-commerce issues); Distance Selling Directive (97/7/EC) which regulates consumer protection in online and remote sales, ensuring that consumers have adequate information and rights in e-commerce; Electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services (eIDAS) Regulation, 2014 which facilitates secure electronic transactions across the EU, promoting trust services like electronic signatures and authentication.

In the EU, as discussed earlier, there exists codified laws on cross border jurisdiction and choice of law in e-commerce including the Rome Convention of 2008 and

Jurisdiction and the Recognition and Enforcement of Judgments in Civil and Commercial Matters (Recast) of 2012, whereas in Nigeria, we do not have any codified law on jurisdiction and choice of law in e-commerce.

The EU's GDPR is stricter and applies globally to companies that handle EU citizens' data, whereas Nigeria's NDPR applies mainly within its borders, although it also applies to foreign entities that handle Nigerian data.

The most remarkable innovation of the EU is the enactment of the European Union Directive on Digital Content and Digital Services 2019,⁴⁶ which regulates digital goods and services sold online, for example software applications, ebooks, streaming services etc. Additionally, the European Union Digital Services Act 2020 was enacted to impose stricter obligations on e-commerce platforms, requiring them to take more proactive measures to monitor and remove illegal content, including counterfeit goods and unsafe products. In Nigeria, no comparable laws exist.

Irrespective of the notable differences, there are similarities between Nigeria and EU E-commerce Laws.

On Data protection, the GDPR in the EU and the NDPR in Nigeria set out regulations for protecting personal data, ensuring that companies comply with privacy standards generally.

On electronic signatures, both the Nigerian Evidence Act 2011 and the eIDAS Regulation in the EU recognize the validity of electronic signatures.

Thus, while Nigeria is yet to enact a comprehensive law regulating e-commerce in Nigeria, the EU have laws on e-commerce already dating back to the early 2000s and even have current laws regulating digital goods and services in e-commerce. However, both jurisdictions share similarities regarding data privacy, even though the EU has implemented more robust and harmonized regulations across its member states.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper has analysed forum and choice of law in cross border e-commerce contracts, and has discovered that in Nigeria, there is no codified law those issues. In

⁴⁶ (Directive (EU) 2019/770).

the EU however, there exists the Rome Convention of 2008 and also the Brussels Recast of 2012 which, though do not expressly provide for e-commerce can be implied as seen in this paper.

This paper recommends that it is imperative to enact a legislation to address choice of law and forum matters with respect to electronic commerce and contracts generally. While the EU laws, particularly the Brussels Recast Regulation, Rome I and II Regulations, provide a comprehensive framework that Nigeria can draw from, for example, including consumer protection provisions, permitting non-EU members or citizens to choose EU for forum selection; modifications are needed to fit Nigeria's local context. Focus areas may include changing EU member states to just the Nigerian territory, determining place of delivery in e-commerce transactions where the place of delivery is online via downloads or grant of software application access, strengthening protection for SMEs by providing options of online dispute resolution and regulating same, and ensuring that the Nigerian jurisdiction is respected by international players. A balance between international standards and domestic priorities is key to effective legislation.

Provisions on choice of law and forum can also be contained in any electronic commerce legislation enacted in the future. Lastly, while parties are free to insert choice of law and forum clauses in their contracts, they should be guided by the exceptions and restrictions discussed above.